

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19322514

Competence And Employability Skills Of SHIM Graduates In South West, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The competence and employability skills of Health Information Management (HIM) graduates are critical for workforce readiness and integration into the health sector. The aim of the study was to assess the competence and employability skills of SHIM graduates in Southwest Nigeria. The objectives included evaluating their technical proficiency, employability readiness, and identifying the challenges faced in securing relevant employment. A qualitative research design was adopted using purposive sampling to select 12 key informants: five recent SHIM graduates, four employers or HR personnel, and three HIM lecturers with over five years' teaching experience. In-depth interviews were conducted, and data collected were transcribed and manually analysed using thematic content analysis to draw out emerging patterns relevant to the research questions. Findings revealed significant digital and IT skills deficiencies among SHIM graduates, alongside gaps in data analytics and health software use. Though communication, teamwork, and leadership were embedded in the curriculum, practical application remains weak. Challenges highlighted included limited job opportunities, lack of employer awareness about SHIM roles, and curriculum misalignment with evolving health data technologies. Nonetheless, efforts to build confidence through presentations and practical exposure were reported. The study concludes that while SHIM graduates possess foundational competence, gaps exist that hinder full employability. It is recommended that HIM schools revamp their curriculum to include practical digital training, promote continuous self-development, and foster collaboration with industry to enhance graduate relevance.

Keywords: Competence, Employability, SHIM Graduates, Health Information Management, Southwest Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Entering the job market as a recent graduate can be challenging, particularly in a competitive environment where employers have numerous candidates to choose from (Mokhtar et al., 2022). To stand out, graduates must possess not only academic qualifications but also the necessary skills and attributes that employers seek (Wynne et al., 2024). Previous studies have highlighted that beyond technical expertise, graduates need to demonstrate essential traits such as responsibility, integrity, dependability, and initiative to increase their chances of employment (Omoniwa, 2017; Wynne et al., 2024). As found by previous research, these attributes play a significant role in employers' hiring decisions, especially at the entry-level (Lameck, 2024). Furthermore, scholars have noted that

workplace behaviours, attitudes, and values are often shaped by an individual's social, historical, and economic experiences (Elsayed, 2024; Xing & Jin, 2023).

The rapid transformation of healthcare systems globally has heightened the demand for professionals equipped with both technical competence and employability skills (Lohans, 2024). Health Information Management (HIM) plays a crucial role in ensuring the efficient handling, storage, and dissemination of health data, which directly impacts healthcare service delivery (Omokanye & Adepoju, 2024). As the health sector continues to embrace digitalization and advanced information systems, the need for well-trained graduates with the ability to adapt to evolving technologies, regulatory requirements, and workplace demands has become imperative (Han et al., 2019). In Nigeria, the healthcare sector faces challenges related to workforce capacity, skill gaps, and the ability of graduates to meet industry expectations (Jensen & Lassen, 2020). The School of Health Information Management (SHIM) plays a pivotal role in training professionals for the HIM sector (Umar, 2024). However, concerns have emerged regarding the extent to which SHIM graduates possess the necessary competence and employability skills required for successful integration into the job market (Adeleke, 2015).

Moreover, in the healthcare sector, Health Information Management (HIM) professionals are expected to combine their technical expertise with employability skills to meet industry demands (Adebayo et al., 2019). While a degree in HIM provides a foundational understanding of health data management, electronic health records (EHRs), and regulatory compliance, employers increasingly prioritize skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, adaptability, and teamwork (Adebayo & Gbabe, 2021; Lohans, 2024). Research has shown that recruitment processes favour candidates who can apply their knowledge effectively in real-world settings (Jensen & Lassen, 2020; Kryukova et al., 2022). Employers are not only looking for graduates with academic credentials but also individuals who possess interactive and interpersonal skills necessary for efficient workplace integration (Zainal et al., 2023).

Competence refers to the combination of knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes that enable individuals to perform tasks effectively in a specific field (Wynne et al., 2024). It encompasses both technical expertise and soft skills, ensuring that individuals can meet job requirements and adapt to evolving workplace demands (Omoniwa, 2017). In Health Information Management (HIM), competence includes proficiency in medical coding, electronic health records (EHR) management, data security, and regulatory compliance, alongside critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills (Sibiya et al., 2023).

Employability is often associated with key competencies, workplace readiness, and the ability to transition smoothly into the labour market (Mokhtar et al., 2022). It encompasses a combination of technical knowledge, soft skills, and personal attributes that enable graduates to secure and sustain employment while contributing meaningfully to their profession and society (Mwita et al., 2024). According to existing literature, employability is defined as the ability of graduates to gain initial employment, maintain their jobs, and progress within their careers (Tushar & Sooraksa, 2023).

Despite the structured training programs in HIM schools, the transition from academic settings to professional practice is not always seamless (Flite et al., 2023). Many graduates struggle with real-world applications of theoretical knowledge, workplace adaptability, and meeting employer expectations (Zainal et al., 2023). The gap between academic training and industry needs raises questions about curriculum adequacy, teaching methodologies, internship exposure, and the effectiveness of professional development programs (Adeoye et al., 2023). With increasing competition in the healthcare job market, the ability of HIM graduates to secure employment and demonstrate competence in their roles becomes a critical issue that requires empirical investigation (Dzomeku et al., 2024). This study focuses on assessing the competence and employability skills of graduates from the School of Health Information Management (SHIM) in South West Nigeria to improve training programs and address skill gaps in the HIM profession.

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, graduates of the School of Health Information Management should possess the necessary competence and employability skills to seamlessly transition into the labour market. However, many SHIM graduates face significant challenges in securing employment due to deficiencies in practical skills, critical thinking, and adaptability (Ibeh, 2022). This mismatch undermines the effectiveness of health information management services and hinders national development.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to assess the competence and employability skills of SHIM graduates in Southwest Nigeria. Specific objectives are:

- i. To examine the level of technical competence possessed by SHIM graduates in relation to industry requirements.
- ii. To assess the employability skills of SHIM graduates in Southwest Nigeria.
- iii. To identify the challenges faced by SHIM graduates in securing employment.

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of technical competence possessed by SHIM graduates, and how does it align with industry expectations?
- ii. How proficient are SHIM graduates in key employability skills?
- iii. What are the major challenges SHIM graduates encounter in securing suitable employment?

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Competence and Employability Skills: Competence is defined as the ability to apply knowledge, skills, and abilities effectively in a professional context (Ayorinde et al., 2016). It includes technical and soft skills essential for adapting to workplace demands. Employability skills, such as communication, teamwork, and adaptability, enhance graduates' ability to secure and maintain employment (Lameck, 2024; Idris & Rajuddin, 2022). Studies emphasize the importance of both technical and non-technical skills in bridging the gap between education and industry requirements (Omoniyi, 2024; Zelesniack et al., 2021).

2.1.2 Overview of Health Information Management Education in Nigeria: The history of HIM education in Nigeria began with the establishment of training programs following the founding of the University College Hospital, Ibadan, in 1957 (Osundina & Kolawole, 2018). Current HIM education involves diverse programs, from diploma to degree levels, overseen by regulatory bodies to ensure quality training (Makinde et al., 2016; Adepoju & Opele, 2023). However, many institutions face challenges in delivering high-quality education due to inadequate resources (Lohans, 2024; Babagana et al., 2023).

2.1.3 Challenges in Employment: Fresh graduates in Nigeria encounter numerous employment challenges, including skill gaps, market saturation, lack of work experience, and insufficient career guidance (Morales et al., 2021). Many struggle to meet employer expectations due to a disconnect between academic training and industry needs, which contributes to high unemployment rates (Mokhtar et al., 2022; Idris & Rajuddin, 2022).

2.1.4 Employability of Health Information Management Graduates: HIM graduates face unique challenges in the job market, including a lack of essential technical and soft skills (Jensen & Lassen, 2020). Although the demand for HIM professionals is increasing, many graduates do not possess the required competencies, particularly in digital health tools and communication, limiting their employability (Ijeoma & George, 2023; Han et al., 2019).

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Technical Competence of Graduates: Several studies highlight the discrepancies between employers' expectations and the competencies of graduates (Zelesniack et al., 2021). Research shows that many graduates, while knowledgeable, lack hands-on experience and necessary employability skills, leading to challenges in securing employment (Akeke et al., 2023; Idris & Rajuddin, 2022).

2.2.2 Employability Skills and Job Readiness: Studies reveal that employers prioritize skills like problem-solving, teamwork, and communication (Adebakin et al., 2015). However, many graduates lack these skills, contributing to perceptions of their unemployability (Morales et al., 2021). Efforts to address this gap include adjusting curricula to better align with industry needs (Omoniyi, 2024).

2.2.3 Employment Challenges Faced by Graduates: Factors such as nepotism, economic instability, and geographic disparities in job opportunities severely impact graduate employment (Xing & Jin, 2023; Wynne et al., 2024). Prolonged unemployment has psychological effects, including anxiety and disillusionment, stressing the need for improved career guidance and networking opportunities (Mwita et al., 2024; Tushar & Sooraksa, 2023).

2.3 Theoretical Review

Three key theories inform the understanding of graduate employability:

1. Human Capital Theory: Emphasizes the role of education and skill acquisition in enhancing employability and economic productivity (Schultz, 1961; Becker, 1964).
2. Career Construction Theory: Focuses on how personal experiences and adaptability influence career paths and professional identity (Savickas, 2005).
3. Employability Skills Framework: Identifies essential skills for workplace success, highlighting the importance of both technical and soft skills (Australian Department of Education, Science and Training, 2002).

Among these, Human Capital Theory is particularly relevant, as it directly relates to the study's objectives of assessing how HIM graduates' education and skills impact their employability. The theory can inform recommendations for enhancing HIM education in Nigeria, such as improving internship opportunities and aligning curricula with industry needs

2.4 Conceptual Model

The conceptual model illustrates the relationship between technical competence, employability skills, and graduate employment status. Technical competence, which includes industry-specific knowledge, formal training, and practical experience, ensures that graduates possess the fundamental expertise required for job roles. However, possessing technical skills alone may not be sufficient to secure employment, as employers also prioritize employability skills. These skills, such as communication, problem-solving, adaptability, and teamwork, enhance a graduate's ability to navigate workplace dynamics, collaborate effectively, and adapt to changing job demands. Graduates who exhibit a strong combination of technical competence and employability skills are more likely to secure jobs relevant to their qualifications, maintain long-term employment, and advance in their careers. Therefore, the model emphasizes that while technical competence provides the foundation for job eligibility, employability skills significantly influence graduates' ability to obtain and retain employment in a competitive labour market.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

A qualitative research design was employed, utilizing Key Informant Interviews (KII) to investigate the technical competence, employability skills, and employment challenges faced by Health Information Management (HIM) graduates in Southwest Nigeria. A phenomenological approach facilitated an in-depth exploration of graduates' experiences regarding job readiness and workplace expectations.

3.2 Study Population

The study's population comprised twelve key informants: five HIM graduates who completed their programs within the last five years, four employers or HR professionals who have hired HIM graduates, and three HIM lecturers with a minimum of five years of teaching experience. This selection provided diverse perspectives on the graduates' competence and employability.

3.3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Participants were selected based on specific criteria: HIM graduates from the past five years, employers with experience hiring HIM graduates, and lecturers with significant teaching experience. Graduates older than five years and employers without relevant experience were excluded to maintain a focused study context.

3.4 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A purposive sampling technique was employed, allowing for the selection of individuals possessing specific knowledge relevant to the study's objectives. The sample size of twelve was deemed sufficient, following the principle of data saturation, where data collection continues until no new information emerges.

3.5 Data Collection Instrument

The primary instrument was a semi-structured Key Informant Interview (KII) Guide, consisting of open-ended questions divided into four sections. This guide covered socio-demographic characteristics and thematic areas aligned with the research objectives, including assessments of technical competence, employability skills, and employment challenges.

3.6 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Content validity was ensured by soliciting feedback from the research supervisor, which was incorporated into the KII Guide to enhance its effectiveness before data collection commenced.

3.7 Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected through telephone interviews, each lasting between 30 to 40 minutes. Participants provided informed consent, and interviews were audio-recorded for accuracy in transcription and analysis.

3.8 Data Analysis

Transcriptions were analyzed using manual thematic analysis. Participant confidentiality was protected through coded identifiers, allowing for systematic organization and accurate coding of the data.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, their rights, and the measures taken to ensure confidentiality. Data were anonymized, and sensitive information was securely stored.

This methodology provides a structured approach to understanding the challenges and competencies of HIM graduates, contributing valuable insights to the field.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study is based on the analysis of the perspectives and experiences of stakeholders including Five (5) HIM Graduates who completed their programs within the last five years, four (4) Employers or HR Professionals who have hired HIM graduates, and Three (3) HIM Lecturers with at least five years of teaching experience, about the competence and employability skills of graduates from the School of Health Information Management (SHIM) in Southwest Nigeria. Interviews were conducted among twelve (12) stakeholders and the thematic analysis conducted on the interviews as transcribed verbatim revealed four themes as revealed in table 4.1.

Therefore, this chapter presents the detailed results of the interview.

Table 4.1: Summary of Themes and their Inter-related Sub-themes

S/N	Themes	Sub-themes
1	Stakeholders' perspectives on Technical Competence of SHIM Graduates	Digital literacy and IT skills deficiencies Practical skills gaps in data analytics and software use Need for curriculum alignment with current industry tools and standards Advanced technical training requirements
2	Employability Skills and Readiness	Incorporation of communication, teamwork, and leadership in curriculum Development of confidence through presentations and practical exposure Need for continuous self-development beyond formal education
3	Challenges in Employment	Limited job opportunities and employer recognition issues
4	Recommendations and insights	Curricular recommendations for more practical, digital, and entrepreneurial training

4.2 Stakeholders' Perspectives on Technical Competence of SHIM Graduates

Digital and IT skills deficiencies

Based on the outcome of the interview, some of the participants' perceptions towards digital and IT skills deficiencies are shown below;

"...I have observed that students of Health Information Management actually struggle with digital literacy, which they still have opportunities to even if school provides opportunities or avenues for them to develop the skills. So, they are still struggling with that...." (P1, L, 38yrs, M)

" ... Well, usually most of the students, they have this struggling with ability to adapt to ICT (Integrated Computing Technology)" (P3, L, 43years, M)

" Yes, I am surprised with this HMIS software. For this is my first time of seeing it and I have been trying to get along with it. It has been a lot" (P4, S, 28yrs, M)

4.2 Practical Skills gaps in data analytics and software use

As indicated in the interview, the participants gave their opinions on Practical skills gaps in data analytics and software use.

"...Another aspect that they are struggling with is data analytics and data visualization, which they really need in order to outshine their colleagues when they graduate...." (P1, L, 38yrs, M)

".... So as SHIM students must have at least computer skills. So computer skills vary depending on the kind of job we eventually get to do. But basically, you must be equipped with a computer skill. So all our courses too, you know, by the time we are teaching students, students are also encouraged to do presentation, short-term presentation to sharpen their presentation skill, analytical skill. And they must also do research". (P2, L, 37yrs, M)

"...Yes, because I wasn't fully prepared for using advanced electronic health record system. Some data analysis tools like DHIS2 and others. So, most of our practical were based on manual systems at that time" (P5, S, 29yrs, M)

"...I noticed that, especially when it comes to using statistical packages, after they learn the one they want to learn in school, everything is, they don't remember. Some even, after learning that, they just stop there. Some, they don't even know how to use Microsoft Word. Some, they know how to use them and cannot use Excel properly. And there are some other things. Some cannot even troubleshoot a system..." (P9, E, 35yrs, M)

4.3 Need for Curriculum alignment with current industry tools and standards

As indicated in the interview, the participants gave their opinions the need for curriculum alignment with current industry tools and standards.

"...Actually, I ensure that the content of curriculum are adequately covered and there is opportunity for students to create interactive sessions to discuss trending things in Health Information Management. Then during that, we will be able to discuss required skills for them to remain relevant even after graduation...." (P1, L, 38yrs, M)

".... what I do is to bring the contemporary needs in different spheres of work engagement of life into the classroom by sharing knowledge on how students can navigate their path, especially when it comes to management courses, the demands that is expected of them, the skills, the leadership skills expected of them, and the quest that many of these industries are expecting from them. I try to infuse that while not deviating from the curriculum of learning." (P3, L, 43yrs, M)

4.4 Advanced Technical Training Requirements

Participants' opinion on the need for specialization and advanced technical training requirements

".... One of the skills I acquired during my HND is statistical package for social sciences and MS Excel. And these skills really helped me a lot in my project writing and in analyzing data too." (P8, S, 27yrs, M)

"...I discovered that their technical performance is not optimal. There are certain levels of technical responsibilities or technical know-how that you should actually meet up to. But most of the employees, most of the SHIM graduates I've employed, they've not met that standard." (P9, E, 35yrs, M)

"...the world is moving around health business analyst as a specialty. So for you to be a health business analyst you must be good with Power BI and me learning these tools are very, very important for me" (P7, S, 26yrs, M)

4.5 Employability Skills and Readiness

Communication, teamwork, and Leadership skills

As indicated in the interview, the majority of participants opined on incorporating communication, teamwork and leadership in curriculum. Some of their comments are shown below;

"... Definitely these are not left untouched because there is curriculum, there is what we call health planning and management. They will do it, health planning and management 1, 2 and 3. They are exposed to use of English, communication in English, communication in health information management. Even recently our board has introduced a course that they call literary appreciation and oral composition. So, all these aims at impacting all these skills into our students" (P1, L, 38yrs, M)

"Yes, they are in the curriculum, but actually, it is like I said, it is beyond what is in the curriculum. We are talking about the outside world. In the school now, if you are given an assignment, you may get it right, you may copy from each other, but by the time you go out, they want you to display what you have, what you are, what you do. That is when you can show your expertise..." (P2, L, 37years, M)

"...Yes, I would say communication skills because that is very important. Because as first part of contact in the hospital, you have to develop a very good communication skill. Then another thing is punctuality. You have to be very punctual. Then willingness to learn too. And respect for others. This has really helped me both during job interviews and in keeping my job..." (P5, S, 29yrs, M)

"...Yes, most of them have the skills. Well, I can't say for all Southwest, but the ones I have met in Ile-Ife, which is my local community, yes, they possess communication skills. Communication skills, I would say, let's say like 60%. Teamwork, I would say 60% as well. Then time management, still the same 60%, just a little bit above average. Not that they are perfect, just a little bit above average...." (P9, E, 35yrs, M)

"That is good customer relation. That is a good communication system..." (P6, S, 28yrs, M)

4.6 Development of confidence through presentations and Practical Exposure

As shown in the interview, some of the participants mentioned development of confidence through presentations and practical exposures. Some of their comments are displayed below;

“... So we make sure that on a weekly basis we post them on practical for them to acquire practical skills. That by the time they graduate they will be able to work confidently as maybe a staff in a particular department or even to work as a group with other healthcare professionals” (P1, L, 38yrs, M)

“.....this school has often time engaged students in getting boldness and developing confidence to go to the job market. Number one, we allow students to go through a series of presentations in class. Like that is what I do in my own class. After every class, the next class, somebody will give a recap. I will choose like five people to give a recap to the class of what we have taught. That's a way of allowing students to build confidence. ...” (P3, L, 43years, M)

“I would say that I was a bit nervous, especially during interviews because we didn't get enough training in that area. You know, what we just teach is normal curriculum. But I believe that they are supposed to also prepare us for the after school. Like how to, you know, face interviewers and all that. So I didn't really get enough training in that area. But I just had to gather it to the workplace through experience...” (P5, S, 29yrs, M)

4.7 Need for Continuous Self-Development Beyond Formal Education

Based on the interview, some participants opined on the need for self-development. Here are some of the responses;

“... The school with the curriculum will expose them to the basics of needed skills, but they have to themselves develop personal development.” (P1, L, 38yrs, M)

：“... basically you are trained as an information management student. You are trained physically about what information management is and practice. But you know, organizations differ. The way federal agency or federal government set its own organization may be different from state, from private. It depends, but your adaptability depends on you...” (P2, L, 37yrs, M)

“..Health information management is an evolving profession and if you do not evolve with time, you are going to be left out of the whole thing. So it's very important that these things, these tools are embedded in you. There are some other skills there, like learning Python. It's not a must for you to learn the whole thing. Just learn the basics, which is just to learn how to do basic, simple analysis, like performing regression, logistic regression using Python...” (P11, E, 55yrs, F)

4.8 Challenges in Employment and Curriculum Improvement

Limited Job Opportunities and Employer Recognition Issues

As indicated in the interview, some of the respondents mentioned that there are limited job opportunities and employer recognition issues. Below are the responses that were made:

“...So, their major challenge is that after graduation, those that want to work with international agencies, they feed us back that we still have to engage on special training before they can fit into these NGOs, international opportunities...” (P1, L, 38yrs, M)

“it's a very competitive one. The government don't have much people. We have many people that are graduating; probably a role of five people, 20 people are applying, 50 people are applying. You know, it will be a very equal task, so few will get the job. It's not everybody that's going to get the job. So, one of the challenges that I see is that many people don't actually prepare enough. Many people don't actually prepare enough, though some will still prepare” (P2, L, 37years, M)

“The main challenge was limited job openings. Many, because many hospitals were either not recruiting or only wanted people with connections. And some even preferred to even employ clerical staff, I mean, not professionals. Maybe probably because they could not pay for the professional. So, these are issues. So, some employers also didn't understand what SHIM graduates could offer” (P5, S, 29yrs, M)

“Usually, the main problem is when hiring a SHIM graduate, the first question or the first issue is, okay, what are they going to bring on the table? What are the things they are going to necessarily make us, you know, before you employ somebody, the person must bring a particular set of value to the organization” (P12, E, 55yrs, M)

4.9 Recommendations and Insights

Curricular recommendations for more practical, digital, and entrepreneurial training

The responses are shown below:

"...Because I would love that some of our curriculum now, some of the content has developed to solve yesterday's problems. But today's issues are things that have gone digital. So if they consider in terms of the standard of job description of educational professionals, they should integrate all those skills in our curriculum "(P1, L, 38yrs, M)

"All I can say is that the curriculum should be more tailored to practical applications rather than theoretical applications, theoretical agendas. The work should be much practical explicit in such a way that all these tools that we are talking about should be included in the curriculum of learning so that students are graduating with all those things at the end of the day. "(P3, L, 43yrs, M)

"Okay, what I think they should include in their curriculum or curricula is we are undergoing some program now which I like. I have been hearing from the students still in school. I wish I had lived from the junior students in school as their alumni, that they are having their entrepreneurial classes. But now, they need to move from teaching them all this physical work to add on desk entrepreneur. What I meant by add on desk entrepreneur is like teaching them how to make use of some software from school, providing them with the mindset of: Okay, from school you know how to develop a website, from school you know how to develop all these interfaces, all these HR interfaces. Once they have the idea, that's an entrepreneur aspect to leverage on when they leave the school. "(P7, S, 26yrs, M)

4.10 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from this study show a notable deficiency in digital and IT skills among SHIM graduates, a concern echoed across stakeholders. Despite available institutional resources, many students still struggle with basic digital literacy. This aligns with Mokhtar *et al.*, (2022) who observed that digital learning tools are underutilized in most tertiary institutions training due to weak integration into course delivery. Adeleke *et al.*, (2015) argued that without foundational ICT knowledge, students are unlikely to meet industry expectations, particularly in industries that requires digital literacy.

Moreover, another key finding is the practical skills gap in data analytics and software use, which many respondents associated with students' inability to function optimally in real-world settings. Supporting this, Idris & Rajuddin, (2022) emphasized that most students in Nigeria lack hands-on experience with hospital information systems, making them less competitive in both public and private sectors. The participants further noted that SHIM curricula do not sufficiently reflect current industry tools and standards, despite individual educators making efforts to bridge the gap. Zelesniack *et al.*, (2021) found that some programs often retain outdated syllabi that fail to evolve with emerging technologies. Abas & Imam, (2016) also reported a misalignment between graduates' competencies and employer expectations, especially regarding digital compliance. Mokhtar *et al.*, (2022) observed that although lecturers sometimes introduce relevant tools informally, the absence of institutionalized support or regulatory updates leaves much of this effort fragmented.

Moreover, the findings underscore the need for advanced technical training and specialization among SHIM graduates, especially in roles requiring proficiency in tools like Power BI and SPSS. Precious *et al.*, (2024) observed that as the health information field expands into areas like predictive analytics and AI, there is a demand for mid-level professionals with advanced analytical training. Similarly, Srikanth, (2025) maintained that advanced skills like scripting in R, performing SQL queries, or building dashboards in Power BI are becoming mandatory for employability. Furthermore, based on the employability skills of the SHIM students, the findings indicate that while communication, teamwork, and leadership skills are integrated into the SHIM curriculum, their application and effectiveness remain uneven. Participants acknowledged that courses such as Health Planning and Management and Communication in Health Information Management aim to instill these competencies, but noted a gap between theoretical acquisition and practical demonstration. This aligns with Krishnan *et al.*, (2025) who noted that many graduates struggle with interpersonal dynamics and

leadership expectations in multidisciplinary healthcare teams. Similarly, Bucăța & Rizescu, (2017) argued that although communication skills are taught in many school's program, they are not often assessed in real-world scenarios, such as role-playing or collaborative tasks, which weakens retention. Abdulraheem *et al.*, (2023) emphasized that HIM professionals are often the first point of contact in health institutions, making communication and teamwork essential not just for employability but also for patient satisfaction and care coordination.

Another key finding is the development of confidence through presentations and practical exposure, which participants identified as a positive but inconsistent feature of SHIM programs. Regular presentations, departmental postings, and recap exercises were highlighted as beneficial in building boldness and workplace readiness. However, some students still expressed low self-efficacy, especially during job interviews, attributing it to limited structured exposure to soft-skill training or mock professional engagements. Mwita *et al.*, (2024) similarly noted that confidence-building interventions in Nigerian tertiary institutions are usually left to chance, resulting in uneven outcomes among graduates. The interviews also revealed a strong emphasis on the need for continuous self-development beyond formal education. Participants expressed that while the curriculum provides foundational knowledge, students must take personal initiative to expand their skillset in line with workplace demands. This sentiment echoes Tushar & Sooraksa, (2023) who highlighted that the rapid evolution of digital tools in health information management requires professionals to update their competencies regularly to remain relevant. Elsayed, (2024) similarly argued that adaptability and lifelong learning are crucial determinants of employability into many professions, particularly in Nigeria, where institutional curricula often lag behind technological advancement.

Moreover, the findings reveal that graduates of the School of Health Information Management (SHIM) in Southwest Nigeria face considerable challenges related to limited job opportunities and lack of recognition from employers. Several participants indicated that even after graduation, many SHIM graduates are required to undertake additional training to qualify for roles in international agencies, suggesting a skills mismatch or perceived inadequacy in their qualifications. This aligns with Lameck, (2024) who found that many health records graduates in Nigeria are often sidelined in favour of general clerical staff due to misconceptions about the scope of their professional contributions. Furthermore, the competitive job landscape, characterized by limited openings and high applicant volume, particularly in public health institutions, exacerbates the situation, as noted by Wynne *et al.*, (2024).

In addition, findings highlight a critical need for curricular reform in Schools of Health Information Management (SHIM), emphasizing practical, digital, and entrepreneurial training to enhance graduate readiness for evolving workforce demands. Participants consistently noted that the current curriculum is outdated, with some course content still addressing obsolete healthcare challenges rather than equipping students with tools for contemporary digital health systems. This concern mirrors the observations of Udofia, (2021) who argued that programs in Nigeria often focus heavily on theory, leaving graduates underprepared for digital workflows and automated record systems. Umar, (2024) also found that limited integration of practical digital tools into health records curricula contributes to skill gaps in software usage, electronic health records (EHR), and health data visualization. Furthermore, Galvão *et al.*, (2020) emphasized the importance of embedding entrepreneurial education into training as a response to rising graduate unemployment and the need for innovation in health information services.

5.0 CONCLUSION

SHIM graduates in Southwest Nigeria possess foundational competence but face gaps in digital skills and employability, hindering job readiness. The study highlights the need for curriculum reforms to enhance practical training and industry alignment. Recommendations include revising the SHIM curriculum for digital tools, integrating soft skills, establishing simulation labs, and fostering industry collaborations. Future research should explore longitudinal impacts and national comparisons. These

findings contribute to bridging education-industry gaps, improving graduate employability, and informing policy.

5.1 RECOMMENDATION

1. Integrate core digital and entrepreneurial skills (e.g., coding, website design, e-commerce) across all subjects to ensure work-ready graduates.
2. Replace or supplement theory-heavy exams with project-based, competency assessments (portfolios, capstones, pitches).
3. Invest in sustained teacher training in digital pedagogy and entrepreneurship and formalise industry/alumni partnerships for mentorship and internships.

5.2 IMPLICATIONS FOR HEALTH INFORMATION MANAGEMENT (HIM) PRACTICE AND EDUCATION:

1. Curriculum alignment with digital health needs, HIM programs must embed digital health competencies (electronic health records, health informatics, data governance, interoperability standards) so graduates can manage clinical data workflows and support digital transformation in healthcare.
2. Emphasis on practical, hands-on training, move from theory-heavy instruction to lab-based, simulated, and project-oriented learning (EHR simulations, data entry/validation tasks, coding and billing exercises, health data analytics projects) to produce practice-ready HIM professionals.
3. Strengthened data quality and governance skills, train students in data quality assurance, privacy/security (HIPAA-like standards), ethical handling of patient data, and record-keeping protocols to reduce errors and support compliance.
4. Development of informatics and analytics capacity, include basic programming, SQL, BI tools, and descriptive analytics in the curriculum so HIM graduates can extract, clean, and interpret health data for decision-making and reporting.
5. Interprofessional collaboration and communication, teach HIM students to work with clinicians, IT staff, and administrators through multidisciplinary projects and placements to improve data capture, workflow integration, and user-centered system design.
6. Integration of entrepreneurship and service delivery models, encourage innovation in digital health services (telehealth support, health information startups, practice consulting) by teaching business models, digital service design, and small-scale enterprise skills.
7. Continuous professional development and credentialing, establish pathways for ongoing CPD (micro-credentials, short courses) in emerging areas (AI in health records, interoperability, data protection) to keep the HIM workforce current.
8. Industry partnerships for experiential learning, formalise collaborations with hospitals, health tech firms, and alumni to provide internships, capstone project briefs, mentorship, and employment pipelines.

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